

Views of classic Uzbek scholars on the development of the civil service institute

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Abstract. In the article, the requirements for civil servants are analyzed in national-historical sources, in particular, "Avesta", as well as the ideas contained in the works of Abu Nasr Farabi, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Nizamulmulk, Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi. Based on these ideas, ideas about the possibility of improving the public service have been put forward even today.

Keywords: public administration, public service, state civil service, public servant, personnel, Uzbek scholars, Avesta.

Scholars have focused on the origin of the civil service that it was formed in a professional manner, that civil servants were selected on the basis of certain abilities. In particular, researchers such as A. Paludan [1], C. Zhua and M. Warner [2] emphasize that the professional public service was created in Ancient China. B. Elman, a scholar of Chinese studies from the USA, noted that an important factor in the state administration of the Ancient Chinese Empire was the examination designed to select the most suitable candidates for public service. That is, the Chinese civil service was based on the principle of meritocracy. This system meant that any Chinese, regardless of family lineage (social background), could become a major state official [3].

Another group of researchers, in particular I.Galnoor and J.Oser, think that the origin of civil service is not only related to Ancient China, but also that talented civil servants were selected in the Old Kingdom of Egypt (mid-3rd millennium BC). Thus, the first buds of public service were formed in the Ancient East. In the Middle Ages, Byzantium, Iran's Sassanids, the Abbasid dynasty of the Arab Caliphate, and the Ottoman Turks established a civil service system. In the new era, civil service developed in Prussia and France in the 18th century, and as a socio-legal institution, it emerged in Great Britain in the 19th century [4].

In 1806, at the initiative of the East India Company of Great Britain, a college was established in London to improve the qualifications of the British officials in charge of India and pass their certification [5]. By the middle of the 19th century,

the process of accepting a candidate for public service through an exam, having certain knowledge and skills to occupy a certain position, as well as hierarchical (vertical) growth of public officials was used under the general term "civil service".

Although the category of public service was formed in Europe, views on the qualities that should be considered when choosing public officials are also included in national historical sources.

One of the important sources in this regard is the holy book of Zoroastrian religion "Avesta", which also covers some issues related to state administration and public service. Historians A.Sagdullayev and U.Mavlanov points out that the hierarchy of public servants is given in "Avesta": "there were civil service officials such as kavi (head of the country), dahyupati (head of a region - several districts), khanjamana (head of a district), vispati (head of a village community), nmanopati (head of a household) from top to bottom." [6] According to "Avesta", democratic means of appointing leaders were used in the territory of our country even before our era. In particular, the political scientist F. Ravshanov rightly states that "if we pay attention to the fact that the appointment of state officials was called for through elections, we can witness the use of populist methods of selecting leaders in the early stages of the history of our statehood." [7]

Along with the Arab conquest of the VII-VIII centuries, the Islamic religion, culture and administration entered the territory of our country. This, in turn, served to create the first Renaissance in Central Asia in the IX-XII centuries. Many scientific works were created during this period. Some of them were devoted to issues of fair, people-friendly state administration. The work of Abu Nasr Farabi (873-950) "City of Virtuous People" is especially important in this regard. The work presents the training, selection and requirements of civil servants in a systematic way [8]. It can be said that the important aspect of this work is that it is far from utopian (fantasy) views and is based on empirical studies and practical life.

Another thinker, Yusuf Khos Hajib (11th century), in his work "Kutadgu bilig" ("Knowledge that leads to happiness") offers the most fair criteria for the selection of civil servants, especially leading personnel, using the example of figurative heroes. Speaking about the requirements for a leader, Yusuf Khos Hajib pays special attention to his spiritual image: "His actions and behavior should be pleasing to many people, and his language should be the same. Those who have shame and have no dirty language are worthy of this. Those who are sharp-eyed, intelligent, knowledgeable, sensitive, and able to distinguish between good and bad are worthy of ministry." [9]

Another important source on public service is the work "Siyasatnama" ("Siyar ul-muluk") by Nizamulmulk (11th century). Nizamulmulk worked as a minister in the Seljuk state (1038-1308). He was a minister with very good qualities. His personality was highly appreciated by statesmen and scholars. For example, Amir Temur respectfully remembers Nizamulmulk in several places of "Amir Temur's codes", among others, he says: "Malikshah Saljuqi dismissed his minister Nizamulmulk. The minister was full of good qualities. In his place, he appointed a low-born, bad man as a minister. Due to the vile deeds, oppression, and selfishness of this minister, the building of the kingdom began to collapse." In the work "Siyasatnama", along with Sharia rules, based on the characteristics of a secular state, management rules for state officials were recommended. These rules of management can even be recognized as "management arts". In particular, Nizamulmulk, speaking about the provision of personnel for the civil service, notes that "selecting officials correctly, assigning them the tasks and tasks that are within their power, assigning one action to one person and expecting from him the virtue of obedience and execution are the main requirements of the state administration." [10]

The great statesman Amir Temur's views on public service were described in "Amir Temur's codes", and some of the qualities of civil servants highlighted in it are still relevant today. In particular, Amir Temur believed that people with the skills of prudence, patriotism, politeness and hard work should occupy leadership positions: "Ministers should be among the people who have these four qualities: the first is nobility and pure lineage, the second is intelligence, prudence, the third is awareness of the condition of the sipahu raiyat, politeness towards them, and the fourth is patience and peace-loving." [11] Temurologist, academician B. Akhmedov emphasizes that Amir Temur created a compact management system: "as for the central state system, it has only seven ministers: 1) the minister of country and raiyat, 2) the minister of security, 3) the minister of financial affairs, 4) the minister of state affairs; the fifth, sixth, seventh ministers - border ministers were in charge." [12]

Our great-grandfather Alisher Navoi lived a fruitful life as a poet, writer, and statesman. His opinions on this matter are expressed in the works "Saddi Iskandari" and "Mahbub ul-Qulub" ("Beloved of the Heart") [13].

Lawyer F.A. Muhitdinova, while researching the political and legal doctrines of Eastern thinkers, emphasizes that the ideas on personnel policy in them are of great importance in training and improving the qualifications of state power and management personnel, including management personnel [14]. In addition to these points, it is possible to say that the ideas of the above thinkers can be a methodological source for improving the legislation on personnel policy.

In conclusion, public service is an important element of public administration and is carried out by professional personnel - civil servants. Although the concept (institution) of public service was created in Great Britain in the 19th century, it essentially began to take shape in the Ancient East, mainly in Egypt and China, in BC. The requirements for staffing the civil service are found in national-historical sources, in particular, "Avesta", as well as in the works of Abu Nasr Farabi, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Nizamulmulk, Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi, most of which are still relevant today.

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